

Piezo 1, a candidate for terminal density reversal of healthy red blood cells

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Author Contributions

AC, KD, and AB planned the study. AB supervised the study. IH and JG provided the samples. AC and KD performed experiments. AC and KD analyzed the data. All the authors discussed the findings. AC, KD, and AB were writing the manuscript. All authors discussed the text and agreed with it.

Competing of Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Significance

The heterogeneity of human red blood cell population is evident from the degree of variance in several physiological properties exemplified by the terminal density reversal of some senescent cells. This phenomenon has been reported a decade ago, however, the mechanism and the candidate protein(s) are still largely unknown. The present study identifies the mechanosensitive Piezo1 channel as one of the candidate proteins mediating density reversal of “senescent-like” cells. We also propose a novel hypothesis of how this channel, along with plasma membrane Ca^{2+} and Na^+/K^+ pumps, is contributing to density reversal in these cells.

Abstract

Density reversal of senescent red blood cells (RBCs) has been known for a long time, yet the identity of the candidate protein(s) is still elusive. While performing Percoll density gradient separation of RBCs from healthy individuals and their subsequent characterization, we identified a fraction of cells in the low-density fraction (~0.025% compared to total RBCs population) which shows reversal in their densities along with the characteristics of cellular senescence. Additionally, we found that these cells are overloaded with Na^+ and Ca^{2+} despite maintaining membrane integrity and therefore, we designated these cells as “senescent-like” cells. In addition to a facilitated Na^+ extrusion by Na^+ , K^+ -ATPase, we found altered ion transport via Piezo1 in these cells. Pharmacological modulation of Piezo1 showed us that Piezo1 and, possibly, other nonselective cation channels by promiscuously transporting Na^+ and Ca^{2+} play an important role in producing these low density “senescent like” cells.

Introduction

Ca^{2+} ions play crucial roles in the aging process of red blood cells (RBCs) [1, 2]. The dynamic equilibrium of intracellular Ca^{2+} ions in RBCs are maintained by its influx-efflux machinery. Ca^{2+} influx is mediated by a combination of ion channels and putative leaks [3]. In human RBCs, plasma membrane Ca^{2+} ATPase (PMCA) is the sole candidate mediating Ca^{2+} efflux as they lack $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger [4]. Aberration in the channel and pump activities are well-known changes that are associated with RBC aging as well as with abnormal hydration of RBCs under different pathophysiological conditions [5-10].

RBC aging is associated with changes in cellular hydration. Whereas Ca^{2+} uptake activates Ca^{2+} -dependent K^+ channels and triggers dehydration, Na^+ accumulation is associated with swelling and overhydration of these cells [11, 12]. Loss or uptake of water, that follows Na^+ and K^+ movements in the cells, in turn affects cellular density, deformability and thereby longevity of RBCs [13]. While studying time dependent changes in cellular hydration in K^+ permeabilized RBCs, Bookchin *et al.* [14] found a small fraction of cells (0.03-4% depending on healthy and/sickle cell individual) that fail to dehydrate contrary to the majority of the cells which become progressively dehydrated by the net loss of KCl and water. They further characterized those small fractions of cells having high Na^+ and low K^+ content. Again, in the course of investigating the relation between PMCA activity and RBCs age from healthy individuals, Lew *et al.* [5] also reported the presence of a similar kind of small fraction of RBCs that are unable to dehydrate by K^+ permeabilization and designated them as senescent cells due to their high content of Glycated hemoglobin Hb A1c. In the same study they found an inverse correlation between PMCA activity and RBCs aging. Activation of the non-selective cation channel (Pcat) was considered as one of the mediators of this density reversal. It was also suggested by Lew *et al.* [15] that the enhanced Ca^{2+} content in these senescent cells drives the activation of Pcat leading to enhanced water and Na^+ accumulation which results in lowering

of cell density. These two studies, therefore, indicated the presence of a small fractions of cells that are physiologically senescent but having reversal in their densities. To describe this phenomena, the authors Bookchin & Lew *et al.* [15] first ever coined the term “Terminal Density Reversal” (TDR). However, work from Lutz *et al.* [16] provided evidence which are not in agreement with TDR being a terminal stage for the majority of RBCs. They rather anticipated that this swelling of the senescent cells is “facilitated not only by internal calcium ions, but in addition by mechanical/oxidative damage”. Moreover, the identity of the Pcat which is an important candidate for producing “TDR” cells is still elusive.

While revisiting the senescence markers for the aging of RBCs from healthy individuals [17], we observed a certain percentage of senescent-like cells (0.06-1.74%) in the low density fraction of RBCs, a similar finding from the study of Bookchin & Lew *et al* [5, 14]. In the current study we, therefore, aimed to characterize those cells in terms of their (i) different aging/senescent markers; and (ii) ionic contents, in particular $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ & $[Na^+]_i$. Finally, we aimed to identify possible candidate protein(s) responsible for the density reversal of these cells.

Results

Our previous study, van Cromvoirt & Fenk *et al.* [17], showed that after Percoll density gradient separation of healthy RBCs the L-fraction contains more young cells (4.1a:b ratio=0.82±0.412) while the H-fraction consists of more old cells (4.1a:b ratio=1.53±0.617). After analyzing the distribution of projected area, L-fraction cells were found to have the highest projected area while the difference between M- and H-fraction cells was remarkably less. Notably, we found a small percentage of cells in the L-fraction displaying projected areas as small as the smallest cells from the H-fraction indicating that the L-fraction consists of a mixture of different cell populations [17]. In addition, Makhro *et al.* [8], showed that intracellular $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ is higher in the L-fraction compared to M- and H-fraction. We further

investigated these discrepancies in the L-fraction by looking into the correlation between $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, and the density dependent changes in RBCs from L-, M-, and H-fractions.

Identification of low-density senescent-like cells in “High Ca^{2+} ” cell population

In this current study we analyzed $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ content by monitoring Ca^{2+} -dependent fluorescent signal of the dye Fluo-4 AM by flow cytometry. Along with the Ca^{2+} -dependent signal in majority of cells (normal Ca^{2+} ; Gate B, Fig. 1A) we detect a small sub-population of Ca^{2+} -overloaded cells (high Ca^{2+} ; Gate A, Fig. 1A). As evidenced from Figure 1B, $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ contents in majority of RBCs forming L-, M- and H-fractions are comparable corroborating with the observation from Wesseling *et al.* [18]. However, this is not the case for Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity in the “High Ca^{2+} ” cells (Fig. 1C). L-fraction “High Ca^{2+} ” cells display much higher Fluo-4 intensity compared to M- and H-fractions, indicating their higher $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ content. Again, the abundance of these “High Ca^{2+} ” cells are also variable among different fractions, typically ranging from 0.5-2% depending on the particular RBCs fraction (Fig. 1D). Interestingly, the L-fraction harbored more of the “High- Ca^{2+} ” cells than that of M-fraction (Fig. 1D). Our additional analysis shows a difference in cell-shape related Forward scatter (FS) and Side scatter (SS) changes between “High Ca^{2+} ” and normal Ca^{2+} cells (Fig. 1E & F). As an accepted general mechanism it is well-known that high $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ promotes water loss from RBCs leading to an increase in cell density [11]. Therefore, these data herein indicate the presence of a “subpopulation” of cells in the L-fractions that resist dehydration despite being Ca^{2+} -overloaded and are displaying reversal in their densities. As mentioned above, in our recent study, we reported the existence of a small population of cells in the L-fraction with senescence-like features such as reduced projected area, however, without any detailed characterization [17]. Altogether, these results raise the possibility that these “High Ca^{2+} ” cells are similar to what was reported by Bookchin *et al.* [14] regarding “TDR” of RBCs. Early back in 1987, Horiuchi and Asakura [19] also reported that some dense sickle cells were converted to light

density cells upon oxy/deoxy cycling. These light cells have markedly increased intracellular Na^+ and are low in K^+ . Interestingly, the authors reported that the presence of external Ca^{2+} decreased the formation of these light cells. Later on, study from Franco *et al.* [20] also supported this result. Addition of extracellular Ca^{2+} inhibited the formation of rehydrated, light sickle cell RBCs (SS-RBCs) from dense cells during oxy/deoxy cycling. Therefore, we tested this possibility in our study for the formation of these “High Ca^{2+} ” cells in L-fraction by adding 1.8 mM Ca^{2+} while performing Percoll density gradient separation. As evidenced from Figure 1G, we do not find any significant changes in the percentage of “High Ca^{2+} ” cell formation nor in the level of PS exposure (Fig. 1H). Elevated PS exposure in the outer membrane is an indicator for cellular damage [21, 22]. Physiological aging is associated with the loss of membrane protein such as Band 3, which can be detected by Eosin-5'-maleimide (EMA) fluorescence intensity in flow cytometry [23]. Therefore, we further characterized the aging of the Annexin V positive cells in L-fraction. Flow cytometric analysis of the cells co-stained with EMA along with CD71 and Annexin V shows that, Annexin V positive cells display significantly less EMA fluorescence intensity compared to CD71-positive cells (Fig. 1I). These results strongly suggest that the L-fraction cells which show an elevated level of PS exposure are associated with membrane protein loss and therefore are supposed to be in the senescence stage of life cycle. To indicate RBCs senescence, however, several different aging markers are there as well [24-30]. Nevertheless, due to different experimental paradigm for isolation and separation of RBCs, contradictions prevail for exclusive aging markers. Therefore, with the senescent markers that we used in this current study, we designate low density Annexin V positive cells having reduced band 3 protein abundance as “senescent-like cells”. Considering two different populations of cells in L-fraction having different Ca^{2+} contents, our further analysis shows that, compared to “Normal Ca^{2+} ” cells, the population of “High Ca^{2+} ” cells are enriched with senescent-like RBCs (Fig. 1J). Altogether these data clearly indicate a fraction of senescent-like RBCs that are overhydrated and therefore having low density, are abundant

in L-fraction in Percoll gradient separation of healthy human blood cells. In our subsequent studies, we further characterized these “Senescent-like High Ca^{2+} ” (SLHC) RBCs for their permeabilities towards Ca^{2+} , Na^+ as well as for water. In addition, we also investigated possible cation transport pathway(s) that might be involved in generating these cells.

The low density SLHC RBCs have altered ion transport pathways

As described before by Lew *et al.* [31], SS-RBCs displaying reversal in density have no change in their ionic permeabilities, however, fail to dehydrate in response to valinomycin or ionophore A23187 and Ca^{2+} . Taken together these data suggest that the transmembrane K^+ gradient was dissipated in these cells. We devised a method by utilizing flow cytometry to simultaneously examine the ionic permeabilities as well as the capacity of the cells to dehydrate in response to hypo-osmotic stress. In the presence of hypo-osmotic solution, RBCs swell due to influx of osmotic water followed by the activation of mechano-sensitive non-selective cation channels. Ca^{2+} uptake via these channels activates downstream signaling cascade(s) (Gardos channel) leading to KCl and water efflux. Subsequently the cells dehydrate and regain their shapes [32]. In our present study, we put L-fraction cells in this “rehydration-dehydration cycle” and analyzed the changes in cell shape. Our FS analysis shows that both SLHC and CD71-positive L-fraction cells swell in response to this hypo-osmotic stress (Fig. 2A). However, the difference in magnitude in FS between “before and after swelling” indicates that young CD71 cells start dehydrating and therefore, regaining their shape much faster than SLHC RBCs within the allowed time frame. In other words, the SLHC cells display a compromised ability to dehydrate. The Ca^{2+} -driven dehydration of RBCs, in general, is associated with concomitant active extrusion of Ca^{2+} from the cells by PMCA thus resulting a decrease in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$. Therefore, we performed further analysis for $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ content (Fig. 2B) in the L-fraction cells under this hypo-osmotic stress condition. It is evident from Fig. 2B, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ level is high in SLHC cells compared to young RBCs corroborating with our above mentioned data. Hypo-osmotic stress

enhances $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ in both CD71-positive young cells as well as in SLHC cells. However, within the time frame of the “rehydration-dehydration cycle”, the senescent-like cells are found to have much more $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ (85.28 A.U.) compared to the young cells (9.15 A.U.) (Fig. 2B). Moreover, the percentage of high Ca^{2+} cells increase modestly in SLHC cell population (Fig. 2C). During RBC aging, an heterogeneous abundance of different ion channels and/or pumps as well as changes in their activities are well-known [8, 9, 33]. This part of our results also suggests altered ion transport pathway(s) in these low density rehydrated SLHC cells, however without indicating any specific ion channel/pump. In addition, these results ruled out any possibilities of low ionic permeabilities in these RBCs as well.

Low density SLHC RBCs are loaded with Na^+ compared to young low-density cells

An increased $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, activates Gardos channel, which in turn, by promoting K^+ and water loss, enhances density of RBCs [34]. Therefore, the appearance of low-density SLHC cells in L-fraction in our study again suggests an altered ionic content, in addition to Ca^{2+} , in these RBCs. One of the prominent features of the previously described senescent “TDR” cells is their high Na^+ content. From the mechanistic point of view, it is understandable that this high $[Na^+]_i$ promotes water influx in these cells and therefore leads to lowering of cellular density. Therefore, we intended to examine intracellular Na^+ content in whole RBCs as well as in Percoll separated L-fraction cells by using the dye CoroNa Green-AM in flow cytometry. For discriminating CD71 and Annexin V positive cells, similar to the paradigm in Figure 1I, we first co-stained the cells with CoroNa™ Green-AM along with CD71 and Annexin V and then measured CoroNa Green-AM fluorescence intensity. As currently there is no report available for measuring $[Na^+]_i$ by utilizing CoroNa Green-AM in RBCs, therefore, we calibrated CoroNa Green-AM fluorescence intensity for three different RBC populations with the corresponding $[Na^+]$ (Fig 3A).. We used 10 μ M of the dye throughout our experiments (dye characterization, supplementary Fig. S1). By using the calibration curve in figure 3A, we find that $[Na^+]_i$ in

unfractionated whole RBCs (designated as WB) is ~12mM (Fig. 3C). Our further comparative analysis from Figure 3C clearly shows that unfractionated RBCs displaying Annexin V staining have significantly higher Na^+ content compared to the CD71-positive young cells. While analyzing $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ in Percoll separated CD71 vs Annexin V positive cells, we observed the similar outcome corroborating with the previously reported findings [14, 20]. Additionally, we do not find any significant difference in $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ between unfractionated and Percoll separated RBCs populations (3B & C). These data, therefore, eliminates any possible effects of Percoll fractionation on the change in $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ in different RBCs populations.

Senescent RBCs have declined PMCA activity

In our subsequent studies, we are aiming to identify and therefore investigate the role of Ca^{2+} transport pathway(s) for the enhanced $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ content as well as in mediating density reversal of low density SLHC cells. In an elegant set of experiments, Franco *et al.* [20] demonstrated the formation of low density cells from dense SS-RBCs *in vitro* by continuous oxygenation and indicated the involvement of Ca^{2+} regulatory proteins in this scenario. As mentioned above, in human RBCs different specific as well non-specific channels are there to mediate Ca^{2+} influx, whereas PMCA is the only candidate for Ca^{2+} efflux. Lew *et al.* [17] showed that PMCA V_{max} declines with RBCs age. However, their study [17] provide “no information on whether these differences result from disparities in the number of pumps, in the fraction of active pumps, in the factors controlling the turnover rate of the pumps in each cell”. Notably, the very low number of the low density SLHC cells in our study makes it difficult to determine the hydrolytic activity of the pump in those cells. Nevertheless, we tested the ATPase activity of this pump in all the three L-, M- and H-Percoll separated fractions. A decrease in pump activity with RBCs aging is evident from Figure 4A. In addition, we observe no change in the abundance of the PMCA4 protein in different fractions (Fig. 4B) by western blotting.

Alteration in Piezo1 activity influences low density high Ca²⁺ senescent RBCs formation

It was suggested that the altered cationic content of the dehydration-resistant SS-RBCs that are showing “TDR” is due to an age-dependent activation of poorly selective cation transport pathway(s) [5, 15]. However, the identity of this pathway is currently unknown. Previous studies [14, 35] showed that modulation of Gardos channel activity affects the formation of low-density hydrated cells upon oxy/deoxy cycling. RBCs experience shear stress while in the flow *in vivo* [36] and this shear stress has been shown to activate Piezo channels [32, 37, 38]. Piezo1, in addition to Ca²⁺, has been reported to promiscuously transport Na⁺ as well [39, 40]. In this current study, we therefore investigated whether Piezo1 plays any role in generating the low density SLHC cells and whether Na⁺ overloading in these cells is due to non-selective Na⁺ uptake via Piezo1. To proceed with our aim, we separated RBCs in fractions according to their density and assessed Ca²⁺ and Na⁺ content in the individual SLHC cells using fluorescent dyes in the presence or absence of Piezo1 modulators with or without extracellular Ca²⁺ supplementation. Addition of extracellular Ca²⁺ enhances [Ca²⁺]_i fluorescence intensity in SLHC, however, we do not observe any change in the number of these cells as well as in [Na⁺]_i content (Fig. 5A-C). Subsequent treatment of L-fraction cells with Piezo1 activator Yoda1(1.5μM) further enhances [Ca²⁺]_i (Fig 5A), however, we observe a sharp decrease in the formation of the low density SLHC cells (Fig. 5B) and in their [Na⁺]_i content (Fig. 5C). Moreover, upon Yoda1 treatment, we observe reduction in FS consistent with the shrinkage in the size of SLHC cells (Fig. 5D). These results nicely fits with the well-known crosstalk between [Ca²⁺]_i and cell density; an enhanced Ca²⁺ influx promotes the water loss and thereby enhances cellular density. Nevertheless, these data certainly indicate that (a) Piezo1-mediated Ca²⁺ transport affects generation of SLHC cells; (b) Piezo 1 preferentially transport Ca²⁺ over Na⁺, when we added extracellular Ca²⁺ in plasma like medium. By using unfractionated RBCs, we further confirmed that Piezo1 preferentially transport Ca²⁺ over Na⁺ when Ca²⁺ is available in the extracellular medium. However, we assume that, only the preferential transport of Ca²⁺

over Na^+ via Piezo1 could not account for the decrease in $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ intensity in SLHC cells (Fig. 5C). A subsequent comparative analysis of $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ -dependent fluorescence intensity in CD71 positive cells vs SLHC cells upon Yoda1 treatment in presence of extracellular Ca^{2+} indicates a hyperactive Na^+/K^+ -ATPase in SLHC cells. This follows from the ability of Na^+/K^+ -ATPase inhibitor ouabain to abolish a decrease in $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ caused by Piezo channel activation in Ca^{2+} -containing solution (Fig. 6). Combining these two data we anticipate that Piezo1 mediated Ca^{2+} transport over Na^+ as well as a hyperactive Na^+/K^+ -ATPase leads to the decrease in $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ levels. A hyperactive Na^+ pump in senescent cells displaying “TDR” have also been reported previously by Lew *et al.* [5, 15]. Nevertheless, to confirm the role of Piezo1, we further treated Percoll separated L-fraction cells with Piezo1 inhibitor GsMTx4 (2.5 μM) in presence of extracellular Ca^{2+} in plasma-like medium and apply the same paradigm as above to sort SLHC cells (5A-D). Inhibition of Piezo1 results to a decline in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ as well as $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ intensity and the formation of SLHC cells (Fig. 5A-C). Conceivably the inhibition in the generation of SLHC cells and lowering in their $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ content is not due to addition of extracellular Ca^{2+} . These data rather confirm the role of Piezo1 in generating SLHC cells. In addition, comparison of the effect of Yoda1 vs GsMTx4 (Fig. 5A-D) provides further information. After treatment of L-fraction cells with the inhibitor GsMTx4, we find that the number of SLHC cells and their $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ content is higher compared to Yoda1 treatment. This could be due to the following facts: (i) either GsMTx4 treatment does not completely abrogate ion transportation via Piezo1, which is unlikely in the applied concentration of the inhibitor or (ii) there are some other ion transport pathways that are involved in generating SLHC cells. This possibility is also evident from the FS analysis of the cells treated with GsMTx4 (Fig. 5D). We do not observe any decrease in the size of the cells upon Piezo1 inhibition. Previously reported studies also indicated that different non-selective cation channels are involved in producing density reversal of senescent cells [5, 14, 15]. Nevertheless, altogether from this set of data we conclude that Piezo1 plays an important role in density reversal of SLHC cells. However, we are also certain, in addition to

Piezo1, there are some other ion transport pathways that are also involved in generating low density SLHC cells.

Discussion

In the present study we identify a small fraction of RBCs with senescent-like features which undergoes density reversal. We find these cells in low density fraction along with reticulocytes while performing Percoll density gradient separation. Importantly, we find Piezo1 as one of the candidate proteins involved in terminal swelling of these cells (Fig. 5).

The mechanism of RBCs physiological aging has been studied for a few decades. Physiological aging is accompanied with several different changes that include an enhanced cellular density, reduced enzymatic activities, high oxidative damages, and more [41-43]. Despite decades of research, the aging markers as well the mechanisms for removing damaged or senescent RBCs from circulation are still conflicting and are largely elusive. One cannot ignore the fact that identification of aging markers substantially depends on the isolation of senescence cells. Nevertheless, some of the well characterized signals for the clearance of senescent RBCs from circulation include externalization of PS [44], clustering of RBCs most abundant band 3 protein [45, 46], and conformational changes in CD47 [47]. In the present study, in accordance with the well-established RBCs aging markers, we determine RBCs aging by analyzing 4.1a:b protein ratio and characterize senescent cells by the elevated level of PS exposure and diminished abundance of Band 3 protein. However, keeping in mind the conflict about RBC senescent markers, we designate the characterized senescent cells with “senescent-like” cells.

The reversal in density for a minute fraction of aged RBCs has been known for long time. However, the mechanism is still poorly understood. Altered ionic contents such as high $[Na^+]_i$ and low $[K^+]_i$ have been reported in these low density senescent cells [48]. We observe that individual low density Annexin-positive senescent-like cells are high in $[Ca^{2+}]_i$, but almost

lost their transmembrane Na^+ gradient. Notably, we designate them as SLHC cells. Increased passive permeability for Na^+ and Ca^{2+} is a feature of RBCs undergoing pathologically fast clearance, such as cells from sickle cell disease patients [5, 14, 20]. Activation of non-selective cation channels have been reported to play a major role in the density reversal of senescent sickle cells. However, the identity of the channel(s) as well as the mechanism(s) involved in hyperactivation of these cation channels in a small fraction of senescent cells remains elusive. It might be the difference in abundance of different channels or the excessive share and oxidative stress that triggers the activation of these non-selective pathway(s).

We assume that the observed high $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ in SLHC cells results from PMCA inactivation but not denying the possibility of enhanced Ca^{2+} influx. This is also true for the high $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ content in these cells. Instead of a hyperactive Na^+ pump, these SLHC cells are loaded with Na^+ compared to young CD71 positive cells. Piezo channels nowadays attract special attention regarding the age-dependent densification of RBCs. A whole-cell patch-clamp study on healthy human RBCs by Dyrda *et al.* [49] shows that a brief suction pulse through the patch pipette increases the membrane permeability. The suction pulse through the patch pipette, reminiscent of the similar condition when RBCs experiences shear stress induced by flow or the membrane distortion produced in sickle cell anemia, has been shown to evoke Ca^{2+} influx [49]. Again, in sickle cells, deoxygenation induced Ca^{2+} influx via conductive cation pathway, P_{sickle} , has been reported to be inhibited by the Piezo channel inhibitor GsMTx4 [50]. Interestingly, different studies demonstrated Piezo1 as one of the candidate members of P_{sickle} [51]. It has been suggested that this enhanced Ca^{2+} influx, in turn could stochastically activates Gardos channel [49, 52] and therefore can influence the densification of RBCs. In this context, an interesting study from Ellefsen *et al.* [53] suggest that while Piezo channels diffuses in the plasma membrane can produce Ca^{2+} flickers in a domain of “mechano-transduction events” arising the possibility of microdomain structure formation, similar to the previously reported Ca^{2+} domain [54], within plasma membrane where Piezo channel(s) can have transient

crosstalk/interactions with several other proteins. In addition, the authors suggest that the Ca^{2+} flickers can represent the activity of a cluster of Piezo channels [53]. Herein, we provide evidence that reveals Piezo1, in addition to Ca^{2+} , transports Na^+ in healthy human RBCs and plays an important role, if not solely, in producing SLHC cells. Depending on our results and the existing reports, we therefore suggest a working hypothesis for the density reversal of the senescent RBCs: generation of these low-density senescent cells depends on the transportation of Na^+ and Ca^{2+} via Piezo1 and its reposition with PMCA and, therefore, formation of a microdomain. While traversing through the capillaries, the shear stress activates Piezo1 on RBCs. Although we do not observe any significant difference in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ level in young, mature, and senescent RBCs, however, some populations of senescent RBCs have high Ca^{2+} . As these cells have an inhibited PMCA activity, therefore in addition to global increase in $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$, these cells can have a very high local $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]_i$ to the nearby region of PMCA. A colocalization of Piezo1 (while traversing through the plasma membrane) and PMCA in these cells could inhibit Piezo1 in transporting Ca^{2+} inside the cells. However, activated Piezo1 (and its clusters) still transports Na^+ , and thereby this enhanced $[\text{Na}^+]_i$ mediates water influx and generates low-density senescent cells.

One of the well-known mechanisms of RBCs turnover is the antigenic changes in the plasma membrane (such as Band 3 clustering and changes in CD47 conformation) leading to phagocytosis by macrophages. However, recent research by Klei *et al.* [26] demonstrates another turn over mechanism of RBCs involving their splenic hemolysis; they found human spleen tissue is filled with erythrocyte ghosts. Now a days it is well understood that the heterogeneity of RBCs populations is even greater than previously thought. The reversal in cellular density for a fraction of aged senescent cells could be a possible mechanism for their turn-over via hemolysis. Unlike healthy human RBCs, sickle RBCs have an average lifetime of 20 days. Bookchin *et al.* [14] found approx. 4% of sickle RBCs are undergoing density reversal. Moreover, TDR phenomena has also been documented from patients with β -thalassemia [14]

as well as in patients with diabetes [55]. If “TDR” leads to hemolytic turn-over of RBCs, it could account for a significant fraction of diseased RBCs that are removed each day. Therefore, understanding the mechanism and identification of the candidate protein(s) involved in the density reversal of RBCs could lead to a novel treatment strategy for different RBC pathophysiology

Materials & Methods

Blood samples

Qualified staff draw blood samples from 20 healthy donors with 16 women (25-64 years old) and 6 men (34-51 years old). All subjects had their hypochromic RBCs below 5%, indicating the absence of iron deficiency. Healthy study subjects provided their written informed consent to participate in this study, in agreement with the Helsinki Convention. Blood samples were obtained from Cantonal hospital Winterthur, Switzerland. Li-heparin was used as an anticoagulant.

Red blood cell density separation

Isotonic Percoll density gradient was used to fractionate RBCs according to their density and enrich fractions with young, mature, or senescent RBCs. 90% isotonic Percoll solution (GE Healthcare, Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, UK; density 1.13 g/mL) was diluted with a plasma-like medium ((mM): 140 NaCl, 4 KCl, 0.75 MgSO₄, 10 glucose, 0.015 ZnCl₂, 0.2 alanine, 0.2 glutamate-Na, 0.2 glycine, 0.1 arginine-HCl, 0.6 glutamine, 20 HEPES-imidazole, pH 7.4 at RT). A plasma-like medium was supplemented with 0.1% bovine serum albumin and prepared for each blood sample [56]. In addition, Percoll density fractionation was performed with or without calcium (1.8-2.0 μ M). Percoll tubes were filled with 13mL of isotonic Percoll, topped with 1mL of blood, and centrifuged at 20,000g for 30 minutes at 35°C (Sorvall RC 5C

plus, rotor SM-24). Low (L), medium (M), and high (H) density fractions were collected and were washed three times (2000g, 5 min, room temperature) and resuspended in a plasma-like medium for further characterization.

PMCA activity

RBCs Ca^{2+} ATPase activity was assayed as described by Kofanova *et al.* [57] with several modifications . Aliquots of washed RBCs (final hematocrit 10-15%) were added to the medium having following composition: 50mM Tris-HCl (pH 7.4), 80mM NaCl, 15mM KCl, 3mM MgCl_2 , 1mM EGTA supplemented with 0.01-0.015-% Saponin. The cells were incubated for 15-20mints on ice. To activate the ATPase reaction, the mixture was transferred to 37degree initially for 5mints. To proceed with the reaction, CaCl_2 was added. To have a final conc 10 μM free Ca^{2+} in presence of EGTA, total CaCl_2 concentration was calculated using the <https://somapp.ucdmc.ucdavis.edu/pharmacology/bers/maxchelator/CaEGTA-TS.htm> logarithm. To initiate the reaction ATP (3mM final concentration) was added and the reaction continued for 10 mints. The reaction was stopped by the addition of ice cold 10% TCA. The mixture was centrifuged, and the released Pi was determined according to Dey *et al.* [58].

Flame Photometer

RBCs were placed in pre-weighed pre-dried Eppendorf tubes washed three times ice-cold solution containing 100 mmol/L $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and 10 mmol/L imidazole-HCl buffered when cooled. The obtained cell pellets were weighed before and after drying at +80°C for 72 hours. The water content was calculated between the wet and dry pellet weights. Dry pellets were wet-burned in 0.2 ml metal-free concentrated HNO_3 ($\geq 99.999\%$ trace metals basis). Thereafter, 0.1 ml of the sample is diluted 1:10 with distilled water and intracellular Na^+ and K^+ measured using Sherwood Model 410 flame photometer (Sherwood Scientific Ltd, Cambridge, UK) [59].

Flow cytometry

The following parameters were detected using flow cytometry (Gallios, Beckman Coulter): the geometric mean of forward (FS) and side (SS) scatter, total reticulocyte (RNA staining) and immature reticulocyte counts (CD71 staining), phosphatidylserine on the outer membrane (Annexin V staining), RBC membrane surface area for band 3 (eosin 5-maleimide, EMA staining), intracellular free calcium (Fluo-4 AM), and intracellular free sodium CoroNa™ Green-AM).

1 μ L of blood resuspended in Thiazole Orange (BD Retic-Count TM) measured the presence of DNA. Triple staining was performed with CD71, Annexin V, and Fluo-4 AM (2 μ M) to distinguish between the young (CD71⁺) and senescent cells (Annexin V⁺) and their intracellular calcium content. The three stainings were incubated in a plasma-like medium with 1 μ L of blood together at room temperature for 1 hour in the dark before measurement. In addition, triple staining of CD71, Annexin V, and EMA (0.5 mg/mL) was performed on the L-fraction. After 1 hour of incubation in darkness, excess of EMA was washed three times in a plasma-like medium at 2500g for 30 seconds, and cells were resuspended in 1 mL of a plasma-like medium containing CD71 and Annexin V. After 1-hour incubation in the dark at room temperature, RBCs were measured on the flow cytometry. $[Na^+]_i$ was measured by utilizing the dye CoroNa™ Green-AM by following the protocol of Iamshanova *et al* [60] as well as Negulescu *et al* [61] with substantial modifications as follows: (i) the dye loading was performed at 37°C for 45-60mint; (ii) for calibration of CoroNa Green-AM, fluorescence intensity was recorded for the clamped cells with fixed intracellular Na⁺ concentrations and (iii) Na⁺ K⁺ ATPase was inhibited by K⁺ free solution. The same experimental paradigm as above was used to perform flow cytometry in presence of different modulator: (i) Piezo channel was activated by Yoda1 (1.5 μ M, 30 mint incubation period) or blocked by GsMTx-4 (2.5 μ M, 30 mint incubation period); (ii) Na⁺ K⁺ ATPase activity was blocked with Ouabain(100 μ M) for 45 minutes at 37°C.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed in GraphPad (GraphPad Prism version 8 (8.4.3)). Shapiro-Wilk test was used for checking if the data were normally distributed. Afterward, a paired parametric (Student's paired t-test) or paired non-parametric test (Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test) was used to compare the different groups. More information can be found below the figures.

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Figures

Figure 1. Identification of low-density senescent cells in the "High Ca²⁺" cell population.

(A) Gating of normal and high calcium cells based on their fluorescence intensity in flow cytometry. (B) Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity for the main population of cells gated as "Normal intracellular Ca²⁺" (n = 10). (C) Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity for high [Ca²⁺]_i cells (n = 10) and (D) the number of "High Ca²⁺" gated cells (n = 10) which are significantly different among different fractions (Student's paired t-test). (E) Significant difference in forward and (F) side scatter for the normal and "High Ca²⁺" cells (n = 12) measured by flow cytometry (paired Wilcoxon test). (G) Number of Annexin V⁺ & (H) Number of "High Ca²⁺" in the L-fraction after Percoll density gradient separation without or with 1.8-2.0 μM Ca²⁺ in the medium (n = 4). (I) Band 3 abundance was measured with EMA-fluorescence in the L-fraction of CD71⁺ and Annexin V⁺ cells (n = 4, paired Wilcoxon test). (J) Analysis of the % of Annexin V⁺ cells in normal and "High Ca²⁺" cell population, as distinguished in Figure 2A, (n = 29) shows a significant difference (paired Wilcoxon test). LF: L-fraction, MF: M-fraction, HF: H-fraction, -Ca: without Ca²⁺ in the Percoll separation, +Ca: with 1.8-2.0 μM Ca²⁺ in the Percoll separation. Data in B-J are presented as mean ± SD. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 ****p<0.0001.

Figure 2. Hypo-osmotic stress shows impaired dehydration-rehydration cycle in Annexin V⁺ cells. (A) Forward scatter analysis before and after the hypo-osmotic stress test measured in the flow cytometer (n = 5). (B) Overall $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ was measured with Fluo-4 AM before and after hypo-osmotic stress test (n = 5). (C) Percentage of high Ca^{2+} cells before and after hypo-osmotic stress test (n = 5). Statistically different (). All data are presented as means \pm SD and the significance was tested with Student's paired t-test. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ **** $p < 0.0001$.

Figure 3. Annexin V⁺ cells have high intracellular Na⁺. (A) Calibration of CoroNa Green-AM in human RBCs. The real-time extracellular [Na⁺] (0–150 mM) are indicated; (B) CoroNa Green-AM fluorescence intensity in unfractionated whole blood (WB) and for CD71 & Annexin V positive RBCs; (C) Measurement of [Na⁺]_i in unfractionated whole blood (WB) and for CD71 & Annexin V positive RBCs. All data are presented as means ± SD and the significance was tested with Student’s paired t-test. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 ****p<0.0001.

Figure 4. PMCA activity decreases with the aging of red blood cells. (A) PMCA activity of M- and H-fraction relative to their L-fraction measured with spectrophotometry (n = 3 , paired Wilcoxon test). (B) PMCA4 abundance in L-, M-, and H-fraction was measured with western blot. LF: L-fraction, MF: M-fraction, HF: H-fraction, PMCA4: Plasma membrane Ca²⁺-ATPase. Data in A is presented as mean ± SD.

Figure 5. Piezo1 plays a role in generating "High Ca²⁺" low-density cells. Flow cytometric analysis with Annexin V⁺ cells from the L-fraction. RBCs were incubated presence/absence of extracellular Ca²⁺ (1.8-2.0μM), and with Yoda1 (1.5μM) or GsMTx-4 (2.5μM). (A) Changes in "High Ca²⁺" fluorescence intensity (n = 6) and (B) the % of these cells (n = 6) upon pharmacological modulation of Piezo1 channels (Student's paired t-test). (C) Changes in CoroNa™ Green-AM fluorescence intensity (n = 5, Student's paired t-test) and analysis of the changes in (D) forward scatter (n = 6, Student's paired t-test) upon pharmacological modulation of Piezo1 channels. Data is presented as mean ± SD. *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 ****p<0.0001.

Figure 6. In "High Ca²⁺" low-density cells the Na⁺/K⁺ pump is hyperactivated. CD71⁺ or Annexin V⁺ cells were treated presence/absence of extracellular Ca²⁺ (1.8-2.0μM) and incubated with Yoda 1 (1.5μM) and/or Ouabain (100μM) (n = 3, Student's paired t-test). *p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001 ****p<0.0001.

Figure 7. Proposed hypothesis on how Piezo1 and Na⁺ K⁺-ATPase play role in forming "High Ca²⁺" low-density cells.

Supplementary figures

Figure S1. Concentration range for CoroNaTM Green characterization.

Figure S2. Piezo1 has a preference for Ca²⁺ over Na⁺. (A) [Na⁺]_i and (B) [K⁺]_i concentration was measured with the flame photometer in the presence/absence of extracellular Ca²⁺ (1.8-2.0 μM) or Yoda1 (10 μM) (n = 3 , paired Wilcoxon test).